

Grain Yield, Grain Weight and Protein, Fe, Zn, Se and Phytic Acid Concentrations of Lentil under Dryland Conditions

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Abstract

Lentil seed is rich in protein, essential amino acids, micronutrients and vitamins for human consumption and in developing countries, protein and micronutrient grain legumes, including lentils seeds, generally meet requirements. In the current study, five experimental plots were established at the three different dryland locations in Central Anatolian Plateau of Turkey with a typical continental climate in 2008 and 2009 experimental years. According to the data obtained, it was determined that the measurements showed interaction according to these years and locations. Promising lentil lines, that are evaluated in present study and have high grain yield, thousand grain weight (TGW), protein and micronutrient content, and also have low level of phytic acid (PA) could be used as parents to develop new lentil varieties in future breeding programs.

Keywords: grain yield, lentil, micronutrients, phytic acid, protein, thousand-grain weight

1. INTRODUCTION

Lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medik.) is an annual, autogamous and diploid ($2n=2x=14$) species, and it is the fourth most significant grain legume worldwide after bean, pea, and chickpea (Ates et al., 2018a). Lentil seed contains protein, essential amino acids, micronutrients and vitamins for human consumption, and its straw by-product has a high concentration of protein and micronutrient offering palatable digestible animal fodder (Toklu et al., 2017). In developing countries, protein and micronutrient requirements of both human and animals are generally met by grain legumes, including lentil seeds.

More than two-thirds of the people in the world lack one or more necessary micronutrients in their diet. Iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), and selenium (Se) deficiencies are the most common in many areas, and micronutrient underfeeding is one of the main health problems across the world (White and Broadley 2005, Thavarajah et al., 2011a). On the other hand, myo-inositol 1,2,3,4,5,6-hexakisphosphate, generally called phytic acid (PA), is the primary phosphorus (P) storage form, and it constitutes 50 to 80% of whole grain P (Thavarajah et al., 2010). The PA concentration in lentil seeds has various nutritional implications because it acts as an anti-nutrient for availability of micronutrients. Human diets with a high concentration of PA and low concentration of micronutrients can give rise to several health problems (Thavarajah et al., 2010). This problem could be solved by decreasing the PA level and increasing the consumption of protein and micronutrient rich foods through biofortification strategies (Toklu et al., 2017; Ates et al., 2016; 2018b). Biofortification is described as the enhancement of the consumable plant portion containing protein, vitamins and micronutrients through plant breeding (White and Broadley 2005). One portion of lentils food can ensure a substantial amount of the vitamins and micronutrients humans need to achieve the recommended daily intake level, and therefore it is considered as one of the five healthiest foods and named as a food legume for biofortification worldwide (Kumar et al., 2016). This shows that any amount of

enhancement in micronutrient concentrations in lentil seeds is certainly going to positively affect human health by increasing the necessary micronutrient availability in their diet (Kumar et al., 2016). However, there are only a limited number of studies related to lentil grain quality, especially for lentil grown in dryland conditions.

Lentil is adapted to dryland conditions and traditionally grown in regions where the annual average rainfall is 300 to 400 mm (Aydoğan, 2011). In Turkey, the yellow cotyledon lentil types with large seeds are mainly grown in the highland areas of Central Anatolia (Sarker et al., 2004, Aydoğan, 2011). The nutritional value and protein content of lentil is determined by its genetics and the environmental factors of the growing season (e.g., soil parameters, pH, moisture conditions, agronomic practices, and climatic factors). Seeding time also affects the protein content of lentil (Erskine et al., 1985). One of the most efficient methods to increase lentil grain quality and yield is the effective use of plant genetic resources. Detecting lentil lines that contain a high concentration of protein and micronutrients, and then utilizing these lines in lentil breeding programs are the main objectives to achieve successful crop improvement (Toklu et al., 2017). Thus, the objective of this study was to determine the variations of grain yield, thousand grain weight (TGW), crude protein (CP) and PA contents, and Zn, Fe and Se concentrations of winter- and spring-seeded lentil genotypes in different parts of Central Anatolia for future breeding objectives, such as grain yield, yield components, and biofortification strategies.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Plant Materials

Nineteen lines together with three checks with yellow cotyledons (Pul 11, Kayı 91 and Kışlık Yeşil 21) and three checks with red cotyledons (Çiftçi, Fırat 87 and Yerli Kırmızı) were used in the current study. While Kışlık Yeşil 21, Çiftçi and Yerli kırmızı are resistant to cold, Pul 11, Kayı 91, Fırat 87 and 19 lines are moderately resistant. Detailed information about plant materials used in the present study is given in Table 1.

2.2. Growing Conditions of Lentil Seeds

In 2008 and 2009, five field experiments were established in three different dryland locations in the Central Anatolian Plateau of Turkey, where there is a typical continental climate (Table 2). These locations were the Ankara Haymana Research Station (39°51'N, 32°58'E, 1210 m altitude), Eskisehir Research Station (39°46'N, 30°34'E, 786 m altitude), and Sivas Research Station in Ulas (39°43'N, 37°03'E, 1320 m altitude). The experiment was undertaken on a winter and spring sown basis to compare day length on the characteristics to be investigated (Table 2). The climate of all locations is described as having cold winters, hot and dry summers, and precipitation in winter and early spring. In these locations, the average precipitation varied between 261 mm and 510 mm during the research period. The soil in the experimental locations was slightly alkaline (pH = 7.3 - 8.1), rich in lime (11.9 - 26.1%) and potassium (501 - 2106 kg ha⁻¹), including a moderate level of phosphorus (49 - 145 kg ha⁻¹) and low level of organic matter (1.32 - 2.73%). The available Fe content of the experimental soils varied from 4.90 to 19.45 mg kg⁻¹ and the Zn content from 0.41 to 1.09 mg kg⁻¹.

All the experiments were conducted as randomized complete block design with four replications. The parcel dimensions were 1 x 5m. Each plot consisted of four rows. Each genotype was seeded by leaving 25 cm between rows and 5 cm within each row. Seeding rates were 350 seeds m⁻². Weeds were controlled by the application of Linuron (2.0 kg ha⁻¹) after seeding, and then hand weeding was applied. A 120 kg ha⁻¹ di-ammonium phosphate fertilizer (18 kg ha⁻¹ N and 55 kg ha⁻¹ P₂O₅) was broadcasted before seedings.

2.3. Determination of Grain Yields, TGW and Protein Content of Lentil Seeds

At full maturity stage, the blocks were harvested by hand, and a mechanical device was used for threshing. The seeds harvested from each replication block were cleaned, and grain yields were calculated. The pooled grain samples were mixed thoroughly, and a sample of each lentil genotype was ground in a 3100 Perten laboratory mill (Huddinge, Sweden) to determine the contents of protein, Fe, Zn, Se, and phytic acid. Ten randomly selected plants from each row of parcel were used to calculate TGW.

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Protein content was determined according to the AACCI Method 46-30 (AACCI, 2000) by using Velp-NDA 701 Dumas Nitrogen Analyzer (Usmate, Italy) instrument. The data was provided as nitrogen (N) (%) and protein (%) was determined based on the protein factor (N x 6.25).

2.4. Determination of Fe, Zn, Se and Phytic Acid Concentrations of Lentil Seeds

The Fe and Zn concentrations of the lentil seeds were calculated according to the protocol of Kacar (1972), in which all lentil samples were cleaned by washing with tap water, and then with distilled water. These clean samples were dried at 65 °C before grinding in an analytical grinder (IKA, A11, Staufen, Germany), and 12 mL of nitric:perchloric acid (4:1) was added to the ground sample (2 g). Atomic absorption spectrophotometry (Varian, SpectrAA 220/ FS, California, USA) was used to detect total Fe and Zn concentrations as mg/kg of this wet decomposition (Kacar, 1972; Kacar and Inal, 2008). In order to obtain a linear calibration curve ($r^2 = 0.999$), the standard Fe solutions of 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 ppm and standard Zn solutions of 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, and 1.2 ppm were measured, and each analysis was performed with three replicates.

The Se concentrations of the lentil seeds were determined according to the protocol of Kacar (1972). HNO₃-HClO₄ (4:1) acid mixed was used to digest ground sample (1 g), and a heating protocol rising from 100 to 200°C in 2 hours on a digestion block was performed. The solutions were adjusted to a 50 ml final volume with ultrapure water, and inductively coupled plasma – mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) with an Agilent 7700 instrument was utilized to detect the Se concentration of these samples (Kacar and Inal, 2008). Calibration curve graphs were prepared using the standard solution of Se (Cat no: 1197960100, traceable to SRM from NIST SeO₂ in HNO₃, $\rho = 1000$ mg/L Se, Merck, Darmstadt, Certipur®, Germany), and each analysis was repeated three times (Gupta et al., 1998)

PA was analyzed according to the protocol as described by Haug and Lantzsich (1983), using a UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Hitachi U-1800). The light absorbance was measured at 519 nm. The correlations between the protein content and Fe, Zn, Se and phytic acid concentrations of the lentils evaluated from values of genotype were calculated using Microsoft Excel 2010.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

MINITAB (University of Texas, Austin) and MSTAT-C (Version 2.1 Michigan State University, 1991) JUMP (version 7.0, SAS Institute Inc.) software were utilized to separately analyze data from each location.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Grain Yield TGW of Lentil Genotypes

The grain yield of the lentils across the locations (Eskişehir, Sivas and Haymana in Turkey), genotypes (19 lines and 6 checks), and cropping seasons (winter and spring) averaged 1,459.7 kg ha⁻¹, varying from 220 to 2,780 kg ha⁻¹ and indicated a ~12.5-fold variation (Tables 3-8). These great variations (~12.5-fold) observed among the grain yield of these lentil genotypes used in the current study may be due to the differences in growing seasons (winter and spring) and the environmental conditions in the different locations, weather conditions, and soil properties. In addition, a higher variation was observed in the grain yield of the advanced 19 lentil lines when compared to the six check genotypes (Table 3-7). The results indicated that these advanced lentil lines had the potential to increase grain yield in lentil when they used as a parent in lentil breeding programs. Similar to our results, previous studies indicate that large genetic variations exist in the grain yield of lentil genotypes (Erskine, 1984; Erskine et al., 1985; Solanki et al., 1999; Sarwar et al., 2010; Tyagi and Khan 2011; Vanda et al., 2013; Mekonnen et al., 2014; Sharma et al., 2014; Ekanayake et al., 2015; Toklu et al., 2017).

The overall mean grain yield of the lentil genotypes grown in winter and spring cropping seasons was detected as 1,743.5 and 1,034 kg ha⁻¹, respectively, indicating that the grain yield of the winter-seeded lentil was ~70% higher than that of the spring-seeded lentil (Table 8). These results clearly showed that winter seeding led to potentially higher yields and produced a greater grain yield than spring seeding, and also winter-seeded lentil crop received sufficient rainfall for a long time compared to spring seeding in dryland conditions. Supporting the results in the current study, Sakar et al. (1988) reported that planting in early winter provided a 50% yield increase in Turkey, and Silim et al. (1991) obtained 22% more grain yield

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with mid-November planting than traditional February planting in the rain fed conditions of Mediterranean basin. In another study, Muehlbauer and Mcphee (2007) found that fall-seeded winter-hardy lentil cultivar 'Morton' produced high yields that exceeded the average yield of spring-planted lentil varieties by 108% and that of the best-yielding spring lentil variety by 73% in several locations of Northwest USA.

Grain yield is a significant plant characteristic utilized in breeding strategies for the selection and detection of genotypes with high grain yield, and it is one the main parameters utilized in breeding programs to achieve crop improvement (Toklu et al., 2017). In the current study, the highest grain yield was detected in line-18 (2780 kg ha⁻¹) grown in Eskişehir during the 2008-2009 winter cropping season (Table 3). This line reached its highest Fe content when grown in Eskişehir, and therefore it can be utilized as a parent in future breeding programs in this location.

The TGW of the lentils across the three locations (Eskişehir, Sivas and Haymana), genotypes (19 lines and 6 checks), and cropping seasons (winter and spring) averaged 46.6 g, varying from 29 to 78 g and presented a ~2.5-fold variation (Tables 3-8). These results indicated considerable variations among the 19 lentil lines, and their differences from the six check genotypes (Tables 3-7). In previous studies, the average TGW of lentils was reported as 32 g (ranging 11-86 g in 3974 accessions) (Solh and Erskine 1984), 34 g (range 11-86 g in 1,356 accessions) (Hamdi et al., 1991), 32 g (range 11-85 g in 2,278 accessions) (Hamdi et al., 1991), 20 g (range 15-31 g in 21 genotypes) (Solanki et al., 1999), 18 g (range 13.5-22.4 g in 19 genotypes) (Shrestha et al., 2005), 28 g (range 16.8-40.3 g in 39 Turkish lentil landraces) (Karakoy et al., 2012), 30.4 g (range 23.9-36.9 g in 16 lines) (Sozen and Karadavut, 2017), 31.2 g (range 12-51.7 g in 181 lines) (Toklu et al., 2017), and 23 g (range 8.5-55.8 g in 187 accessions) (Mehra et al., 2018). TGW indicates whether the plants had a healthy growth or whether they encountered any stress factor during the development period (Sozen and Karadavut, 2017). The average TGW (46.6 g) obtained in current study was higher than those reported in previous studies. Similar to grain yield, TGW is a significant plant parameter utilized in breeding strategies for selection (Toklu et al., 2017). In the present study, the highest TGW was detected in line-12 (78 g) grown in the Haymana during the 2009 spring cropping season (Table 7), and thus this variety can be utilized as a parent in future breeding programs in order to increase TGW.

The overall average TGW of the lentil genotypes grown in the winter and spring cropping seasons was detected as 44.1 and 50.5 g respectively, suggesting that the TGW of the spring-seeded lentil was ~25% higher than that of the winter-seeded lentil (Table 8). These variations in the TGW of the lentil genotypes are considered to be due to plant responses to environmental and climatic factors.

3.2. Protein Content of Lentil Seeds

Proteins are the building blocks of the human body, and therefore their presence in our routine diet plays an important role in maintaining the body's continuous metabolic activity (Kumar et al., 2016). In the present study, the CP content of the lentils across locations (Eskişehir, Sivas and Haymana), genotypes (19 lines and 6 checks), and cropping seasons (winter and spring) averaged 25.6 %, varying from 19.2 to 28.9% (Tables 3-8). Similar to our results, previous studies indicated that the CP content of lentil seeds varied from 22 to 36.4%, with a mean of 26% (Hamdi et al., 1991; Solanki et al., 1999; Karakoy et al., 2012; Kumar et al., 2016; Khazaei et al., 2019). Supplementing cereal grains with high CP legumes is one of the main criterion in order to improve human diet in poor countries, and for this purpose advanced lentil lines as a parent candidate used in present study have the potential to increase CP content in lentil. In this study, the average CP content of the lentil seeds in winter seeding was slightly higher compared to spring seeding (26.2 vs 24.6 %) (Table 8). This result indicates that seeding time does not greatly affect CP content in typical dryland regions with 300-500 mm rainfall.

3.3. Micronutrient Elements of Lentil Seeds

Micronutrients have various significant functions in metabolism and physiological pathways of both plants and humans, and a deficiency of them creates various vital health problems around the world, especially in developing countries (Ates et al., 2018b). Research to overcome this problem through biofortification is under development, and the main aim is to increase the micronutrient level in that part of the plant that can be eaten by humans (Aldemir et al., 2017).

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The recommended daily intake (RDA) of Fe is 8 mg for males and 18 mg for females (Thavarajah et al., 2009). Fe is the most common micronutrient deficiency affecting approximately 3.7 billion people worldwide and resulting in the death of 0.8 million people annually (Aldemir et al., 2017). Therefore, it is important to develop lentil genotypes with a high Fe content in order to solve this global problem. In the current study, the Fe concentrations of the lentils across the three locations, genotypes and cropping seasons averaged 113.3 mg kg⁻¹, ranging from 79.5 to 157.8 mg kg⁻¹ (Tables 3-8). In previous studies, the ranges of Fe concentrations were reported as 73-90 mg kg⁻¹ in 19 Canadian grown lentil genotypes (Thavarajah et al., 2009), 48.96-81.39 mg kg⁻¹ in 39 Turkish lentil landraces (Karakoy et al., 2012), 50.85-109.8 mg kg⁻¹ in 41 lentil lines (Kumar et al., 2014), 40.54-85.61 mg kg⁻¹ in 234 lentil accessions (Sarker et al., 2017), 19.9-185.7 mg kg⁻¹ in 181 lentil lines (Toklu et al., 2017), and 11.2-110 mg kg⁻¹ in 181 lentil accessions (Mehra et al., 2018). In lentil recombinant inbred line (RIL) populations, Fe concentrations range from 27 to 191 mg kg⁻¹ (Klein and Grusak, 2009) and from 37.2 to 175.7 mg kg⁻¹ (Aldemir et al., 2017). The Fe concentrations obtained from the present study were higher than most of the previous studies, such as reported by Thavarajah et al. (2011b), Karakoy et al. (2012), Kumar et al. (2014), Sarker et al. (2017) and Mehra et al. (2018). Therefore, these lentil lines have the potential to increase the Fe content in lentil. The detected level of RDA for Fe were within the RDA ranges from a portion (100 g) of lentils used in the present study. In addition, the average Fe concentration of lentil seeds in spring seeding was found to be higher than winter seeding (121.5 vs 107.8 mg kg⁻¹) (Table 8), indicating that increasing the temperature regime opened a way to higher Fe accumulation in lentil grains. Similar to our result, Thavarajah et al. (2010) reported that the Fe level in lentil seeds was higher in hotter temperature conditions (116 mg kg⁻¹) than colder temperature conditions (113 mg kg⁻¹).

In the world population, 17% of people are at risk of having inadequate Zn in their diet (Wessells and Brown, 2012), with the main risk groups being newborns, children, pregnant women, and the elderly (Fischer Walker et al., 2009). Annually, more than 100,000 children under the age of five die due to Zn deficiency (Black et al., 2013). The RDA of Zn is generally considered to be 10 mg for children and 12 to 15 mg for adults (Frossard et al., 2000); however, this amount may be too low for vegetarians (Frossard et al., 2000). Zn plays crucial roles in the human body, particularly in protein synthesis (MacDonald, 2000), spermatogenesis and steroidogenesis (Yamaguchi et al., 2009), immune response onset and regulation, vitamin A metabolism (Salgueiro et al., 2000), cell division, energetic metabolism, regulation of DNA transcription (Molkentin, 2000), stabilization of macromolecules, and insulin storage and release processes (Chimienti et al., 2005). It is also important as an antioxidant and enzymatic cofactor (Oliveira et al., 2009).

In previous studies, the Zn concentration ranges were reported to be 44-54 mg kg⁻¹ in 19 Canadian grown lentil genotypes (Thavarajah et al., 2009), 42.3-73.1 mg kg⁻¹ in 39 Turkish lentil landraces (Karakoy et al., 2012), 40.3-75.2 mg kg⁻¹ in 41 lentil lines (Kumar et al., 2014), 22.4-60.4 mg kg⁻¹ in 234 lentil accessions (Sarker et al., 2017); 23.7-96.7 mg kg⁻¹ in 181 lentil lines (Toklu et al., 2017), 18.1-86.2 mg kg⁻¹ in 181 lentil accessions (Mehra et al., 2018), and 40-75 mg kg⁻¹ in 16 lentil genotypes (Rasheed et al., 2020). In contrast, in the current study, the Zn concentrations of the lentils across locations (Eskişehir, Sivas and Haymana), genotypes (19 lines and 6 checks), and cropping seasons (winter and spring) averaged 11.8 mg kg⁻¹, ranging from 10.1 to 14.1 mg kg⁻¹ (Tables 3-8). Thus, it can be seen that the Zn concentrations obtained from the current study are lower than these previous studies. The reason for this situation may be that the soil in the experimental fields used in the current study contains low levels of Zn concentrations (0.41 to 1.09 mg kg⁻¹), and this problem can be resolved by Zn fertilization. Recently, Maqsood et al. (2015) showed that the application of Zn fertilizers increased the grain yield and Zn content of small green lentils in Saskatchewan (Canada), and Rasheed et al. (2020) determined that the application of Zn fertilizers with a higher concentration resulted in higher grain output and higher level of Zn concentration in lentil grains than the lower concentration of Zn fertilizer application. In addition, in the current study, similar to the Fe results, the mean Zn concentration of the lentil seeds in spring seeding was slightly higher than winter seeding (121.5 vs 107.8 mg kg⁻¹) (Table 8). Supporting our result, Thavarajah et al. (2010) reported that the Zn level in lentil seeds higher in hotter temperature conditions (69 mg kg⁻¹) than in colder temperature conditions (61 mg kg⁻¹).

Se is another significant micronutrient for humans, and the RDA of substance was considered to be 55-200 µg for adults in order to be healthy. Low concentrations of Se have been related to various health

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problems, such as cardiovascular disruption, deterioration of eye health, disorders of nervous system, muscular dystrophy, early aging, and developmental retardation in children (Ates et al., 2016). Therefore, it is very important for people to have sufficient Se, and increasing the level of this micronutrient in lentil grains could contribute to the availability of further dietary sources of this micronutrient. In the current study, the Se concentrations of the lentils across locations (Eskişehir, Sivas and Haymana), genotypes (19 lines and 6 checks), and cropping seasons (winter and spring) averaged 0.25 mg kg^{-1} , ranging from 0.18 to 0.31 mg kg^{-1} (Tables 3-8). In previous studies, the Se concentrations ranged from 0.42 to 0.67 mg kg^{-1} in lentils grown in Canada (Thavarajah et al., 2011b) and from 0.07 to 0.96 mg kg^{-1} in lentils grown in Bangladesh (Rahman et al., 2013). In another study, the Se concentration was reported as 0.12 - 0.88 mg kg^{-1} in a population of lentil RILs that consisted of 96 individuals (Ates et al., 2016). Similar to the Zn results, most of the Se levels detected in the present study were lower than those of the previous studies (Thavarajah et al., 2011b; Rahman et al., 2013; Ates et al., 2016). These findings show that seeding time and also temperature regime did not affect the Se level of the lentil seeds. However, as reported by Ekanayake et al. (2015), the application of selenite and selenate fertilizations can increase the grain yield and Se concentrations of lentil grains.

3.4. Phytic Acid Concentrations of Lentil Seeds

It is well known that PA is an anti-nutrient present in legume grains, and at high levels, it inhibits Fe and Zn bioavailability (Welch and Graham, 2004). Therefore, reducing PA levels in grains may provide a partial solution for human micronutrient malnutrition. On the other hand, PA elimination in grains through breeding is not advisable because it is vital to retain micronutrients in grains during development stage (Thavarajah et al., 2011b). In the present study, the PA concentrations of lentils across the study locations (Eskişehir, Sivas and Haymana), genotypes (19 lines and 6 checks), and cropping seasons (winter and spring) averaged 4.4 mg g^{-1} , varying from 1.4 to 7.3 mg g^{-1} and indicated a ~5-fold variation (Table 3-8). Reducing PA in grains via plant breeding has been the focus of efforts to increase Fe and Zn bioavailability for humans, improve the quality of animal feed, and decrease P in animal waste (Thavarajah et al., 2010). In previous studies, the lowest PA concentration of lentil seed was reported as 2.5 mg g^{-1} (Thavarajah et al., 2009), and the results obtained from the current study were lower than any results reported to date (Morris and Hill, 1996; Thavarajah et al., 2010). Therefore, the lentil lines having a low level of PA used in the current study can be considered as parents in future breeding programs when deciding on genotypes that accumulate higher concentrations of Zn and Fe.

In this study, the mean PA content of the lentil seeds in winter seeding was lower compared to spring seeding (4.2 vs 4.7 mg g^{-1}) (Table 8). The PA concentration in lentils varies depending on the geographical locations, genotypes, soil factors, temperature, and other growing season conditions. Similar to our findings, previous studies reported that cooler temperatures during the seed filling period resulted in lower PA concentrations in lentil grains (Thavarajah et al., 2010; 2011b).

3.5. Analysis of Variance

The analysis of variance for both grain yield and TGW for all the locations (Eskişehir, Sivas and Haymana) indicated that location (L), genotype (G) and their interaction (L x G) were highly significant at the $P \leq 0.01$ level (Table 8). These findings indicate that there were significant differences between the three locations and the lentil lines. Since the 19 lentil lines utilized in the present study were grown in different locations and exposed to different temperature regimes, there were important distinctions, which was an expected result. Additionally, the analysis of PA shows that location was highly significant at the $P \leq 0.01$ level, and genotype was significant at $P \leq 0.05$ but their interaction (L x G) was detected to be not significant (Table 8). Supporting our results, previous studies showed that environmental conditions, such as different locations, soil properties, and temperature regime had significant impacts on PA synthesis in lentil grains (Morris and Hill, 1996; Thavarajah et al., 2010). On the other hand, the analysis of variance for protein, Fe, Zn and Se for all the locations showed that only location was highly significant at the $P \leq 0.01$ level whereas the genotype and L x G interaction was not significant. These results showed that the protein, Fe, Zn and Se content of the grains significantly differed only between the lentil lines grown in different locations. This

finding may be due to the different conditions of weather (temperature regime and precipitation) and soil (texture, pH, ventilation or moisture) in the experimental locations.

3.6. Correlation Analysis

The results of the correlation analysis between grain yield, TGW, and protein, Fe, Zn, Se and PA concentrations of lentil grains evaluated from the values of the 19 lentil lines indicated significant positive correlations between the protein content, Fe, Zn, Se, and TGW in the present study (Table 9). The highest positive correlation was identified between the Fe and Se concentration (0.9), and between the Zn and Se concentration (0.8) of the lentil grains (Table 9). This indicates that if one of the concentrations of Fe, Se or Zn increases, the other two will also increase. Supporting our results, positive correlations were reported between the micronutrients in earlier lentil studies showing that similar transporters or pathways manage the uptake and transport of these micronutrients (Karakoy et al., 2012; Mehra et al., 2018). On the other hand, in the present study, a negative correlation was identified between PA and TGW, protein, Fe, Zn, and Se (Table 9). Thavarajah et al. (2010) reported that if PA concentrations increased in lentil grains, Zn concentrations would decrease due to the capability of PA to retain Zn with the complexes of PA-Zn. Similar to PA, grain yield had a negative correlation with grain yield, TGW, protein, Fe, Zn and Se content of the lentil grains in the present study (Table 9). Toklu et al. (2017) reported that grain yield and TGW were positively correlated, and they were also positively correlated with Zn, potassium, magnesium and calcium content but were negatively correlated with the Fe content of lentil genotypes. The reason for the results obtained from the studies being different is that the lentil lines used in the current study were selected according to their grain yield, and therefore no positive correlation was detected between grain yield and other traits.

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Abbreviations: CP, crude protein; G, genotype; ICP-MS, inductively coupled plasma – mass spectrometer; L, location; PA, phytic acid; RDA, recommended daily intake; RIL, recombinant inbred line; TGW, thousand grain weight;

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Table Legends

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Table 9. Correlations between the protein content, Fe, Zn, Se and PA concentrations, grain yield and TGW of lentil genotypes

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Table 1. Information of plant materials used in the study

No	Source	Genotypes	Pedigree	Origin	Color of Cotyledon	Seed Size	Reaction to Cold
1	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 1	Line	ILL39xILL5588	ICARDA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
2	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 2	Line	ILL45xILL2126	ICARDA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
3	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 5	Line	WA8649090xILL1878	USA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
4	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 6	Line	WA8649090xILL1878	USA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
5	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 7	Line	WA8649090xILL1878	USA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
6	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 8	Line	WA8649090xILL1878	USA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
7	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 9	Line	ILL7617xAKM282	ICARDA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
8	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 13	Line	ILL8634	ICARDA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
9	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 17	Landraces	TUR02714	Turkey	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
10	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 21	Landraces	TUR02709	Turkey	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
11	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 22	Landraces	TUR02708	Turkey	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
12	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 23	Landraces	TUR02706	Turkey	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
13	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 26	Landraces	TUR02717	Turkey	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
14	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 29	Line	LC9548009	USA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
15	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 30	Line	WA8649090	USA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
16	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 31	Line	WA8649090xILL1878	USA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
17	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 32	Line	WA8649090xILL1878	USA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
18	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 33	Line	WA8649090xILL1878	USA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
19	TÜBİTAK_YM_VD_2008/ 34	Line	WA8649090xILL1878	USA	Yellow	Small to medium (3-6 mm)	Moderate
20	Pul 11 (check)	Winter green cultivar		Turkey (Ankara University, Faculty of Agriculture)	Yellow	Medium (5.5 mm<)	Moderate
21	Kayı 91 (check)	Winter green cultivar		Turkey (Eskişehir Transitional	Yellow	Medium (5.5 mm<)	Moderate

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			Zone Agricultural Research Institute)			
22	K.Yeşil 21 (check)	Winter green cultivar	Turkey (Ankara University, Faculty of Agriculture)	Yellow	Small (3.5 mm <)	Resistant
23	Çiftçi (check)	Winter red cultivar	Turkey (Ankara-Central Research Institute for Field Crops)	Red	Small (3-4 mm)	Resistant
24	Firat 87 (check)	Winter red cultivar	Turkey (Diyarbakır GAP International Agricultural Research and Training Center)	Red	Small (3-4 mm)	Moderate
25	Yerli Kırmızı (check)	Winter red cultivar	Turkey (Diyarbakır GAP International Agricultural Research and Training Center)	Red	Small (3.5 mm<)	Resistant

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Table 2. Locations, cropping seasons and seeding times of the field experiment conducted in 2008 and 2009

Locations	Cropping season	Seeding time
Haymana	2008-09 winter	October 7, 2008
Haymana	2009 spring	April 8, 2009
Eskisehir	2008-09 winter	October 13, 2008
Sivas	2008-09 winter	September 23, 2008
Sivas	2009 spring	April 19, 2009

Table 3. Grain yield, TGW and protein, Fe, Zn, Se and PA contents of lentil genotypes grown in Eskişehir during the 2008-2009 winter cropping seasons

Line ID	Grain Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Thousand Grain Weight (g)	Protein (%)	Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	Se (mg kg ⁻¹)	Phytic Acid (mg g ⁻¹)
1	2150	52	26.4	114.0	11.9	0.29	4.6
2	2320	57	25.0	113.3	11.7	0.26	5.1
3	1970	35	26.5	113.5	11.6	0.26	5.5
4	1870	36	26.6	112.8	11.9	0.28	5.1
5	1730	34	27.3	111.8	11.6	0.25	5.8
6	2720	29	25.1	113.3	11.7	0.25	4.7
7	1940	38	26.3	113.5	11.7	0.25	5.5
8	2300	63	26.0	110.3	11.8	0.29	5.8
9	2420	65	24.8	112.8	11.9	0.27	4.2
10	1710	38	27.5	114.8	11.9	0.28	4.8
11	2260	49	27.3	113.0	11.6	0.27	5.6
12	2010	54	25.8	112.8	11.9	0.24	5.1
13	2490	59	25.4	114.3	11.9	0.28	4.9
14	1960	37	25.0	114.0	11.8	0.27	4.3
15	1720	35	27.4	113.3	11.7	0.26	6.0
16	1740	36	26.5	114.8	12.0	0.30	4.9
17	2040	29	26.5	114.8	12.0	0.28	5.4
18	2780	29	25.1	114.3	11.8	0.28	4.0
19	2630	29	25.2	113.3	11.8	0.28	5.3
Pul 11	1900	58	27.2	114.0	12.0	0.26	5.4
Kayı 91	2100	47	26.2	112.5	11.9	0.28	4.9
K. Yeşil 21	2040	39	27.8	114.8	11.8	0.27	5.3
Çiftçi	2430	33	26.8	114.8	12.0	0.28	6.3
Fırat 87	2460	36	25.7	115.3	12.1	0.26	5.7
Y. Kırmızı	2180	32	27.3	114.3	12.0	0.28	7.3
Maximum	2780	65	27.8	115.3	12.1	0.30	7.3
Minimum	1710	29	24.8	110.3	11.6	0.24	4.0
Average	2154.8	41.9	26.3	113.6	11.8	0.27	5.3

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Table 4. Grain yield, TGW and protein, Fe, Zn, Se and PA contents of lentil genotypes grown in Sivas during the 2008-2009 winter cropping seasons

Line ID	Grain Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Thousand Grain Weight (g)	Protein (%)	Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	Se (mg kg ⁻¹)	Phytic Acid (mg g ⁻¹)
1	1330	55	24.6	83.0	10.3	0.21	4.4
2	2010	58	24.4	85.0	10.6	0.20	4.1
3	1860	43	23.9	87.3	10.8	0.21	2.8
4	1510	45	25.3	87.3	10.8	0.21	3.2
5	2340	37	25.7	84.3	10.5	0.20	2.8
6	1810	33	23.2	83.3	10.4	0.22	3.6
7	1270	47	23.0	85.0	10.6	0.21	3.5
8	1290	68	23.7	83.0	10.4	0.21	5.1
9	1800	69	24.4	83.0	10.3	0.20	3.9
10	800	43	25.6	83.8	10.5	0.23	4.8
11	1480	69	24.1	84.5	10.6	0.23	4.0
12	1660	64	24.8	84.5	10.5	0.22	3.8
13	1650	62	24.2	84.8	10.6	0.23	3.7
14	1060	42	23.1	79.5	10.1	0.22	3.5
15	1580	43	24.7	83.0	10.4	0.19	3.4
16	2100	38	25.1	87.3	10.9	0.21	2.8
17	1850	31	23.7	85.5	10.8	0.18	3.1
18	1490	33	22.6	84.8	10.6	0.21	4.0
19	1520	31	24.6	85.8	10.8	0.20	4.2
Pul 11	1080	66	25.4	85.0	10.6	0.21	4.3
Kayı 91	1890	56	25.0	85.0	10.6	0.21	3.2
K. Yeşil 21	710	42	24.4	84.0	10.6	0.19	5.2
Çiftçi	1180	37	23.0	86.3	10.8	0.21	4.6
Fırat 87	1040	39	24.1	85.0	10.6	0.22	5.3
Y. Kırmızı	840	36	24.9	85.5	10.7	0.18	5.3
Maximum	2340	69	25.7	87.3	10.9	0.23	5.3
Minimum	710	31	22.6	79.5	10.1	0.18	2.8
Average	1486	47.5	24.3	84.6	10.6	0.21	3.9

Table 5. Grain yield, TGW and protein, Fe, Zn, Se and PA contents of lentil genotypes grown in Haymana during the 2008-2009 winter cropping seasons

Line ID	Grain Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Thousand Grain Weight (g)	Protein (%)	Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	Se (mg kg ⁻¹)	Phytic Acid (mg g ⁻¹)
1	1530	51.7	27.5	123.8	11.9	0.27	4.5
2	1580	52.9	27.8	125.8	12.1	0.28	3.8
3	1670	43.5	28.2	124.0	12.1	0.28	3.0
4	1470	43.0	28.0	124.0	12.1	0.27	2.8
5	1420	39.6	28.8	125.0	12.0	0.27	3.5
6	1690	32.0	27.6	124.5	12.1	0.28	3.4
7	1800	41.1	28.2	124.3	12.0	0.27	3.5
8	2060	56.4	28.2	127.0	12.2	0.28	3.1
9	2030	56.0	26.8	126.0	12.2	0.28	3.9
10	980	36.6	28.4	126.0	12.2	0.28	3.0
11	1430	52.4	27.9	124.0	12.0	0.27	3.2
12	1560	56.0	28.2	126.3	12.1	0.27	3.2
13	1550	54.0	27.6	124.5	12.1	0.27	3.3
14	1600	37.4	28.1	126.3	12.2	0.27	2.7
15	1470	40.1	28.4	126.5	12.2	0.27	4.1
16	1480	39.2	28.6	126.0	12.2	0.27	3.9
17	1400	31.8	28.5	124.5	12.0	0.27	4.6
18	1770	31.1	28.3	125.0	12.1	0.27	3.9
19	1720	31.6	28.1	125.0	12.1	0.27	3.1
Pul 11	1810	60.1	28.9	122.8	11.9	0.27	3.1
Kayı 91	1460	49.3	28.7	127.5	12.3	0.28	3.1
K. Yeşil 21	1530	37.7	28.1	126.5	12.3	0.28	1.4
Çiftçi	1700	31.5	28.8	126.8	12.3	0.28	2.4
Fırat 87	1660	31.8	28.0	124.5	12.1	0.27	2.9
Y. Kırmızı	1370	33.3	28.9	125.8	12.2	0.28	3.3
Maximum	2060	60.1	28.9	127.5	12.3	0.28	4.6
Minimum	980	31.1	26.8	122.8	11.9	0.27	1.4
Average	1589.6	42.8	28.2	125.3	12.1	0.27	3.3

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Table 6. Grain yield, TGW and protein, Fe, Zn, Se and PA contents of lentil genotypes grown in Sivas during the 2009 spring cropping season

Line ID	Grain Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Thousand Grain Weight (g)	Protein (%)	Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	Se (mg kg ⁻¹)	Phytic Acid (mg g ⁻¹)
1	620	56	22.9	98.0	10.6	0.21	6.5
2	740	61	22.5	99.5	10.7	0.21	5.4
3	430	42	22.6	101.0	11.0	0.22	5.6
4	610	48	22.5	99.3	10.8	0.22	5.8
5	350	41	22.7	99.5	10.7	0.21	6.2
6	430	35	22.7	101.3	11.0	0.22	6.6
7	750	50	19.2	103.3	11.2	0.23	5.8
8	870	62	20.8	97.8	10.6	0.25	6.5
9	960	72	22.2	97.5	10.5	0.20	5.1
10	530	39	22.8	98.5	10.8	0.20	6.0
11	910	66	23.3	101.8	11.0	0.20	5.4
12	870	70	22.7	99.5	10.8	0.22	5.7
13	900	66	22.8	98.8	10.8	0.22	5.4
14	810	50	21.1	94.0	10.2	0.23	5.3
15	510	41	24.5	99.3	10.8	0.22	5.7
16	370	39	22.9	101.8	11.1	0.22	6.6
17	220	36	24.2	101.3	11.0	0.20	5.9
18	740	35	22.8	102.8	11.1	0.22	6.9
19	810	35	22.4	101.0	11.0	0.23	5.7
Pul 11	1040	62	22.2	100.8	11.0	0.24	4.2
Kayı 91	600	47	23.2	98.8	10.9	0.20	5.2
K. Yeşil 21	780	50	23.7	100.0	11.0	0.23	6.2
Çiftçi	870	34	22.0	97.0	10.5	0.22	7.3
Fırat 87	490	39	21.8	100.5	11.0	0.23	6.4
Y. Kırmızı	600	36	22.0	101.8	11.0	0.22	7.3
Maximum	1040	72	24.5	103.3	11.2	0.25	7.3
Minimum	220	34	19.2	94.0	10.2	0.20	4.2
Average	672.4	48.5	22.5	99.8	10.8	0.22	5.9

Table 7. Grain yield, TGW and protein, Fe, Zn, Se and PA contents of lentil genotypes grown in Haymana during the 2009 spring cropping season

Line ID	Grain Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Thousand Grain Weight (g)	Protein (%)	Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	Se (mg kg ⁻¹)	Phytic Acid (mg g ⁻¹)
1	1430	62	26.2	141.0	13.5	0.29	3.6
2	1420	71	26.8	142.8	13.8	0.29	4.1
3	1380	44	27.3	142.5	13.7	0.30	2.8
4	1280	45	26.7	144.0	13.8	0.30	3.0
5	1110	41	27.3	142.5	13.7	0.29	3.9
6	1440	46	26.6	141.8	13.6	0.29	3.4
7	1040	53	25.6	142.0	13.6	0.28	2.7
8	1990	73	25.1	142.3	13.6	0.29	3.9
9	1960	77	26.3	144.3	13.8	0.30	3.6
10	1230	47	27.3	138.3	13.2	0.27	3.9
11	1560	76	26.7	142.8	13.6	0.31	4.5
12	1200	78	26.7	141.3	13.6	0.29	3.2
13	1660	77	26.9	144.8	13.9	0.28	3.3
14	1030	44	26.6	139.8	13.4	0.28	3.1
15	1320	44	27.9	141.5	12.9	0.28	3.4
16	1220	42	27.4	144.5	14.0	0.30	3.2
17	1410	35	26.1	143.5	13.7	0.29	3.3
18	1280	36	26.2	145.0	14.0	0.28	2.5
19	1550	38	26.9	144.3	13.9	0.29	2.9
Pul 11	950	69	26.9	136.5	13.1	0.30	2.9
Kayı 91	1440	53	27.0	157.8	14.0	0.31	3.9
K. Yeşil 21	1620	45	27.7	145.5	14.1	0.27	4.1
Çiftçi	1560	39	26.5	144.0	13.8	0.28	4.0
Fırat 87	1570	40	27.2	143.3	13.7	0.28	3.7
Y. Kırmızı	1240	38	27.3	145.0	13.9	0.31	4.1
Maximum	1990	78	27.9	157.8	14.1	0.31	4.5
Minimum	950	35	25.1	136.5	12.9	0.27	2.5
Average	1395.6	52.5	26.8	143.2	13.7	0.29	3.5

Table 8. Averages of grain yield, TGW and protein, Fe, Zn, Se and PA contents of lentil genotypes grown in Eskişehir, Sivas and Haymana in both winter and spring cropping seasons

Growing Season	Locations	Averages						
		Grain Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Thousand Grain Weight (g)	Protein (%)	Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	Se (mg kg ⁻¹)	Phytic Acid (mg g ⁻¹)
Winter (2008-2009)	Eskişehir	2154.8	41.9	26.3	113.6	11.8	0.27	5.3
	Sivas	1486.0	47.5	24.3	84.6	10.6	0.21	3.9
	Haymana	1589.6	42.8	28.2	125.3	12.1	0.27	3.3
Spring (2009)	Sivas	672.4	48.5	22.5	99.8	10.8	0.22	5.9
	Haymana	1395.6	52.5	26.8	143.2	13.7	0.29	3.5
Average		1459.7	46.6	25.6	113.3	11.8	0.25	4.4
Winter Average		1743.5	44.1	26.2	107.8	11.5	0.25	4.2
Spring Average		1034.0	50.5	24.6	121.5	12.3	0.25	4.7
Loc.F		**	**	**	**	**	**	**
Var. F		**	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	*
Loc. x Var. F		**	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

** : Significant at % 1

* : Significant at % 5

ns: Not significant

Loc.: Location

Var.: Variation

Table 9. Correlations between the protein content, Fe, Zn, Se and PA concentrations, grain yield and TGW of lentil genotypes

	Protein	Fe	Zn	Se	Phytic Acid	Grain Yield	Thousand Grain Weight
Protein	1.0						
Fe	0.7	1.0					
Zn	0.5	1.0	1.0				
Se	0.7	0.9	0.8	1.0			
Phytic Acid	-0.2	-0.3	-0.2	-0.1	1.0		
Grain Yield	-0.7	-0.7	-0.6	-0.6	0.2	1.0	
Thousand Grain Weight	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	-0.1	0.0	1.0